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First approach of analyze the Characteristics of additively manufactured components

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Abstract

Additively manufactured (AM) components in many cases require post-processing by machining operations in order to attain required surface finishes or tolerances and to remove support structures. These post-processing processes, often milling, pose significant challenges on the tool with regard to vibration and interrupted cuts which can lead to high tool wear rates. The tool wear may occur as a result of specific microstructural and mechanical characteristics of the AM components. Recent research shows that metal AM parts show higher strength compared to cast parts but reveal anisotropic properties. The requirements for machining AM components are thus complex and require a profound understanding of the component properties and machinability to allow for a reliable and sustainable post processing of metal AM components. In the context of this work, AM parts manufactured with SLM (Selective Laser Melting) and WAMM (Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing) processes are analyzed with regard to microstructure and mechanical characteristics using nickel- based alloys, high strength steel and titanium alloys as representative sample materials that are difficult to cut. Anisotropy and hardness gradients were stated for all AM parts analyzed. Tool wear, component surface quality and process stability in milling processes.

Keywords: Additive manufacturing; Inconel; SLM

1. Introduction

Additive manufacturing as a key technology of the fifth industrial revolution enables cost-efficient production of complex near-net-shape components. Particularly in the aerospace and energy sectors highly stressed components with complex, often bionically optimized structures are required.

In these areas, highly resilient materials such as nickel-based or titanium alloys in combination with additive manufacturing processes can be used to produce components and structures in a cost-efficient and resource-saving manner.

Selective Laser Melting (SLM) as a powder bed-based metal additive manufacturing process is widely used in industry due to its component density of over 99%, the dimensional accuracy of the as-built components and the microstructure which is adjustable by means of process parameters. However, additively manufactured components cannot be used entirely without "conventional" ablative manufacturing processes such as milling or grinding. In particular, the high-quality requirements in the field of aerospace applications with regard to dimensional accuracy and surface quality require mechanical post-processing in addition to subsequent heat treatment. Furthermore, functional surfaces such as sealing surfaces or threads must be manufactured according to the required qualities. Particular attention is paid to the removal of support structures in the powder bed-based AM processes.

Due to the local (point-by-point) heat input and the layer-by-layer structure in the SLM process microstructural peculiarities arise in the components compared to cast components. Initial investigations show a columnar structure in the built-up direction. [1, 2] The recurring cyclic heat input with high temperature gradients and rapid extraction rates in the melting areas provide a special characteristic, anisotropy in the built-up direction of the microstructures of additively manufactured components. [3] This study investigates special characteristics with reference to machinability and presents resulting properties. More closely this study aims at identifying any anisotropies in the mechanical properties in built direction (Z) that might occur as a result of cyclic heat input during SLM.

2. Materials and experimental procedure

2.1. Test specimen

The test specimen has been produced using the metal additive manufacturing process SLM. It describes a cuboid with an angled overhang which is supported as seen in figure 1. After the additive built process, the specimen was heat treated.

Figure 1 test specimen for analyses

The nickel-based superalloy Inconel 718 test specimen has a nominal chemical composition (wt.-%) of Ni 45.93, Cr 24.78, Fe 20.04, Nb 6.3, Ti 1.9. Support structures and the overhang were cut off so that a solid sample with dimension of 100 mm x 40 mm x 8mm (length x height x width) was then divided into 28 samples of 12 mm x 10 mm x 5mm (length x height x width) demonstrated in figure 2. 14 samples were chosen perpendicular to the built-direction (A) and 14 lateral to the cross section (B), as shown in figure 3. This preparation routine allows to characterize the microstructure in a 3-dimensional orientation and to derive causes for the specific mechanical properties. It is then possible to identify the requirements for machining post processing in more detail.

Figure 2 sample order of the test specimen

Figure 3 Orientation of sample cutting for microstructure investigation

The arrangement of the two types (A) and (B) was randomly sorted. The reason for the random arrangement of the specimen orientation is based on the fact that the investigations should show a good overview of the microstructure of the components. Possible local defects in certain process steps or areas of the components can influence the results. So that these possible errors do not influence the results, the orientations of the specimens are evenly distributed over the component.

2.2. Experimental Procedure

As described by Renhof, 2007 [4] it is not possible to derive the strength of Inconel718 directly from the hardness.

However, the mechanical properties are well appraised by hardness measurements and first results further supported by measurement of the grain size and closer investigations of the coarser phases using light optical methods.

The studies can be classified into two subsequent steps:

- Hardness measurement for mechanical properties
- Microstructural investigation of test samples

The hardness gradient measurement was implemented with a fully automated hardness tester Carat 930 (ATM). The hardness measurements were carried out according to DIN EN ISO 6507 Vickers microhardness test with a test load of 1 N (HV 0.1) [4]. Also, Vickers hardness measurement are carried out with a test load of 100 N (HV10). 24 single measurements on each sample are done to ensure reliable mean values.

For microstructural analysis, a light microscope, model Axioscope 2 MAT (Zeiss), was used. To describe the microstructure of the samples three magnifications are used, 50x, 100x and 200x. In accordance to the ISO 643:2019 "Steel-Micrographic determination of the apparent grain size" the averaged grain size of the samples were determined at a magnification of 100x [5]. In addition, layer thickness and spotsizes of the microstructure were measured via a 3D-digital microscope VHX 5000 (Keyence) offering a magnification of 1000x. To identify the different phases of the Inconel 718 samples a scanning electron microscope (SEM) Jeol JSM-IT100 was used. The sample preparation followed the working instructions of the Federal Institute of Materials Research and Testing BAM. Etching was conducted using an

Inconel 718 solution (75 ml Ethanol (96%) / 25 ml HCl (37%) mixed with 3 ml H₂O₂ (30%).

Using the area counting method according to [5] and number of grains, the number of grains per mm², average grain area, average grain size and grain size index were determined.

3. Results

3.1. Mechanical Properties

Figure 4 shows the results of the Vickers microhardness test in built-direction. The average minimum and maximum hardness values of four test samples are presented. The hardness of the test samples is nearly constant about 300 HV0.1 with a slight decrease in built direction from the bottom 335 HV0.1 to the top 313 HV0.1. This accounts for a relative decrease of 6.5 %. Based on the results of the measurements the mechanical properties regarding hardness are isotropic.

Figure 4 Hardness gradient Vickers micro hardness testing

One possible explanation for the small decrease in hardness could be residual stress of the additively manufactured element [6]. Important factors could also be the geometry (support structures), the different coefficient of thermal expansion of the fabricated part and the base plate, the different thermal history of the individual layers as well as the selected heat treatment [1, 6–8].

3.2. Microstructural investigation

The results of the grain size measurement are shown in Table 1. The grain sizes become smaller in the built-up direction of additively manufactured components.

Furthermore, the maximum grain sizes in the individual component sections were determined during the grain size analysis. Averagely, grain sizes decrease with increasing component height. In the range from 0 to 10 mm starting from the bottom of the component the maximum grain size is 251 μ m and in the range from 30 to 40 mm 134 μ m. This accounts for a difference of approx. 50 %. The average grain size also decreases by 50 % from 118 μ m near the built platform to 67 μ m in the uppermost area of the part. In contrast to the hardness measurements, the microstructure analysis clearly reveals anisotropies in the built-up direction. This finding is contradictory to the hardness measurement as if the grain size decreases the hardness increases due to the increased number

of grain boundaries. In this work the hardness values decrease with decreasing grain sizes.

Table 1 Averaged Grain size in built direction

sample	17	sample	18
magnification	200x	magnification	200x
number of grains	9	number of grains	20.5
m (grains/mm ²)	71	m (grains/mm ²)	164
grain size index G	3	grain size index G	4
\emptyset -grain size in μ m	118	\emptyset -grain size in μ m	78
max. grain size in μ m	251	max. grain size in μ m	168
sample	19	sample	20
magnification	200x	magnification	200x
number of grains	32	number of grains	80.5
m (grains/mm ²)	256	m (grains/mm ²)	220
grain size index G	5	grain size index G	5
\emptyset -grain size in μ m	63	\emptyset -grain size in μ m	67
max. grain size in μ m	194	max. grain size in μ m	134

The light microscopic investigations of the microstructure in vertical orientation (A) show the single melting pools of the laser paths, see figure 5 a). The average size of the melting pools is about 80 μ m along the sample height. No differences in layer thickness were noticed along the built height. This finding in combination with the averaged and maximum grain size concludes that several grains grow across the single layers. Epitaxial grain growth can be identified as a reason for propagating grain growth over several layers. The grain structure shown in figure 5 b) clearly proves that during the SLM process the cyclic heat input initializes grain growth over multiple layers.

Observing the microstructure in horizontal orientation (B) the single laser paths are visible. The paths of two consecutive layers have an angular offset about 67°, so that a meander hatching is used for the manufacturing process [9].

Figure 5 Laser scan paths a) magnification 100x b)

Figure 6 microstructure a) bottom layer b) top layer of the test sample magnification 500x

The microstructure formed during the very rapid solidification in the SLM process consists of grains growing in the built-up direction (figure 6). As said before the grains grow over the single layers as can be seen in figure 5b. Although some columnar structures are only slightly visible due to heat treatment. Light microscopic examination shows the arrangement of the different phases in the microstructure of Inconel 718. Within the face-centered cubic (fcc) γ matrix of Ni, the γ' phase formed from the alloying elements titanium (Ti) and Aluminium (Al) is regularly arranged. The different phases show up as darker components in the image. They are arranged in thin layers nearly perpendicular to the growth direction of the grains.

The differences in the shape of the precipitates along the height of the component are significant. In the lower area, near the building platform, the precipitates are strongly developed and also clearly visible within the microstructure, see figure 6 a). The cross section of the precipitates decreases with increasing component height as demonstrated in figure 6 b). Most likely less heat is introduced in the higher component layers compared to the lower layers resulting in decreasing thickness.

First results reveal that the mechanical properties show no significant anisotropies and differences compared to conventionally produced Inconel 718. A slight hardness gradient can be detected but is not decisive to determine an influence on the machinability. For a well-founded and far-reaching estimation of the mechanical properties on machinability tensile tests have to be carried out. However, the microstructural investigations show anisotropic properties in built direction from the bottom layer to the top layer of the sample. These may influence the machinability of additively manufactured components using SLM:

- Firstly, the columnar grain structure may have an influence on the chip removal process.
- Secondly, increasing numbers and characteristics of strength-increasing precipitates can be seen in the lower area of the components. These may influence tool wear and cutting forces during the process.
- Thirdly, the gradient of decreasing grain sizes along the built-up direction may also cause severe anisotropies.

Figure 7 Location of the samples from figure 6

4. Conclusion

In this study the mechanical properties and the microstructure of additively manufactured Inconel 718 have been investigated by means of hardness testing and optical analysis with regard to machinability. The SLM process leads to anisotropic characteristics of the microstructure. The three main characteristics are:

- Columnar grain structure in built-direction
- Increasing and more dominant precipitates along built-direction
- Decreasing gradient of grain size in built-direction

The anisotropic microstructure most likely influences the material properties and therefore the machinability of AM Inconel 718. This hypothesis will be supported by future tests such as quasi-static ship formation process investigations.

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